

The mechanism of sand erosion of glass mat reinforced plastics

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ABSTRACT

The sand erosion behavior of glass mat reinforced plastics was investigated, and the effect of angle of attack and glass contents on erosion rates were clarified. Based on these results and the SEM observations, the mechanism of erosion damage was discussed and the method to estimate the erosion rate of glass mat composite was also proposed. In this method, the rule of mixture was used which included the erosion rates of matrix resin and high fiber fraction specimen. The calculated values by this equation agreed well with the experimental results.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Sand erosion; Fiber, glass; Matrix, polyester; Rule of mixture

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, FRP have widely used in the aerospace, ships, other transportations and chemical industries, because of their high specific strength and good corrosion resistance.

Erosive phenomena, materials removal by impact of solid particles, have been a serious problem in many industries, then it was discussed and reviewed by many researchers on homogeneous materials such as metals and plastics[1]~[4]. But erosion problem will be recognized also on FRP members. For example, FRP pipes for seawater are eroded by sand particles sucked with seawater.

We have been studying on the sand erosion of plastics to make clear the erosion behavior, characteristics and mechanisms of damage[5],[6],[7]. In this paper, the sand erosion characteristics of the glass mat composites was investigated and also the method to estimate the erosion rate of glass mat composites was discussed.

2. EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

Sand blast type erosion apparatus is shown in Figure 1. The two phase flow, air mixed with the glass powders with diameter of 350 μm , is produced in the ejector, and then this flow impinges the test specimen placed 2 cm away from the nozzle tip at room temperature. Weight change was measured after testing by a balance with a sensitivity of 0.01 mg.

Impact velocity of glass particles was 24.5 m/s and angle of attack (α), angle of P-O-A in Figure 2, was varied from 20° to 90°. As shown in reference[5], [6], the fiber orientation (β), angle of A-O-B in Figure 2, has great inference on erosion damage of FRP. So, in case of attack with low angle, β was changed from 0° (parallel attack on fiber) to 90° (perpendicular attack on fiber).

Unsaturated polyester resin and its composites with glass fiber (mat) were used as a specimen. Glass contents of mat specimens were varied from 0 (resin) to 40wt.%. And the unidirectional specimen

of high glass contents was also tested to investigate the effect of fiber orientation (β) on damage.

Figure 1 Schematic diagram of erosion tester.

Figure 2 Definitions of angle of attack (α) and fiber orientation (β)

3. RESULTS

The typical example of weight loss with time for 20wt.% mat specimens at various attack angles was shown in Figure 3.

Erosion damage of glass composites increased with increase of mass of impacting particles lineally. This behavior was observed in all experimental conditions. Erosion rates are calculated as average slopes of these cumulative erosion-time curves. And these rates were converted to volume erosion rates to compare each FRP having different densities.

The erosion rates tested at various conditions, angles of attack and glass contents, were shown in Figure 4. From this figure, some characteristic results were recognized.

First, the erosion rates of composites were affected by angle of attack. Secondly, this effect of angle of attack was varied with the glass contents. At lower angles of attack, the erosion rates were smaller with increase of glass fiber contents. The maximum erosion rates of FRP was obtained at higher angle of attack in comparison with the matrix resin. This tendency means that the erosion behavior of mat FRP is controlled by a brittle mode damage, and this behavior was emphasized with increase of glass fiber contents.

The eroded surfaces were observed by SEM. From these observations, the different erosion damage appearances between higher angle of attacks and lower angle of attacks were recognized. But the

eroded surface of the matrix part in the FRP was the same as that of resin specimen without glass fiber at any angle of attack. On the other hand, the erosion behavior of glass fiber in the FRP was largely affected by angle of attack. At lower angle of attack, especially, the angle between impact direction of particle and the direction of fiber orientation gave the serious effect on the behavior of the erosion damage[5],[6].

Figure 3 Erosion-time curve of FRP at various angle of attack.

Figure 4 Effect of angle of attack and glass contents on volume erosion rate of FRP.

4. Discussion

4.1 Rule of mixture

For practical use of FRP with high reliability, it is very important to estimate the erosion rate. The rule of mixture which is very popular to estimate the strength of composites was applied to the erosion rate of FRP. As shown in equation (1), erosion rate of mat FRP ($(E_c)_{\text{mat}}$) is given by rates of matrix (E_m) and fiber (E_f), and volume fraction of glass fiber (V_f).

$$(E_c)_{\text{mat}} = \frac{E_m \cdot E_f}{E_m \cdot V_f + E_f \cdot (1 - V_f)} \quad (1)$$

If this equation is hold, we can get the constant fiber erosion rates, by substituting experimental data of E_m and $(E_c)_{\text{mat}}$ at various fraction. But as shown in Figure 5, the fiber erosion rates were not constant. Thus the rule of mixture is not applicable in this style for estimating the erosion rate.

The reason why the equation (1) was not valid to estimate the erosion rate is that the equation contains the erosion rate of a fiber. SEM observation showed that fibers were eroded by a bundle, not by a filament[5]. Then in case of mat FRP, erosion rate of a bundle (strand) (E'_f) should be used instead of E_f in equation (1). At the same time, fiber bundle fraction V'_f should substitute for V_f in equation (1). Thus following equation was derived.

$$(E_c)_{\text{mat}} = \frac{E_m \cdot E'_f}{E_m \cdot V'_f + E'_f \cdot (1 - V'_f)} \quad (2)$$

And fraction of fiber bundle were determined by SEM observations.

$$V'_f = \frac{100}{58.0} V_f \quad (3)$$

In order to obtain the erosion rate of a fiber bundle, we made unidirectional specimens which contained very large fraction of glass fiber. In these specimens, as mentioned above, fiber orientation β have a great effect on erosion rate, at lower angle of attack α , then the effect of β was examined.

The results were shown in Figure 6. Because fiber bundles are dispersed uniformly with $\beta = 0^\circ \sim 90^\circ$, average value based on approximate curve should be used. This curve is drawn by a function of $\sin^2 \beta$, because the damage is proportional to the kinetic energy obtained by perpendicular velocity component to the fiber ($V_p \cos \alpha \sin \beta$)².

Figure 5 Calculated erosion rate of fiber by equation (1).

Figure 6 Effect of fiber orientation on erosion rate.

The calculation result by equation (2) was shown in Figure 7 at $\alpha = 30^\circ$ and 90° . These results showed good agreement with experimental data. But equation (2) is not available without experimental data for E_f' . Then establishment of more general equation to estimate the erosion rate of glass composites is necessary.

Figure 7 Comparison of experimental and calculated erosion rate at various volume fractions of glass fiber.

4.2 Erosion rates of fiber bundles

To obtain more general equation, it is very important to know the erosion rate of fiber bundles. As shown in Figure 8, the particle velocity can be divided to two component, parallel to the specimen surface, $V_p \cos \alpha$, perpendicular to the specimen, $V_p \sin \alpha$. And the component $V_p \cos \alpha$ can be also divided to two components, parallel to fibers, $V_p \cos \alpha \cos \beta$, perpendicular to fibers, $V_p \cos \alpha \sin \beta$. Among these components, $V_p \cos \alpha \cos \beta$ can be neglected, because parallel attack to

Figure 8 Components of particle velocity.

fibers have a little effect on erosion rate[6].

Therefore, erosion rate of fiber bundles E_s is assumed as equation (4)

$$E_s = A(V_p \sin \alpha)^m + B(V_p \cos \alpha \sin \beta)^n \quad (4)$$

where $A, B, m, n = \text{constant}$

Equation (4) was transformed into following equation.

$$\frac{E_s - A(V_p \sin \alpha)^m}{B(V_p \cos \alpha)^n} = \sin^n \beta \quad (5)$$

From the experimental results of unidirectional high fraction specimen, m was obtained as 1.33. And as shown in Figure 6, erosion rate changed with $\sin^2 \beta$ approximately, then n was obtained as 2.

A and B are determined by substituting $\beta=0^\circ$ and 90° at constant α into equation (5). Then

$$A = 2.54 \times 10^{-6}$$

$$B = 1.0 \times 10^{-6}$$

Figure 9 shows calculated values and experimental values at $\alpha=30^\circ, 45^\circ$. It is recognized that equation (5) hold very well. Then we can estimate the erosion rate of fiber bundle at any particle velocity, α and β .

4.3 Erosion rates of mat FRP

By using equation (3),(5) and erosion rate of matrix resin, erosion rates of mat FRP can be estimated. But as mentioned in 4.1, at inclined impact, the average erosion rate for all over fiber orientation β should be used. An average erosion rate of fiber bundles are obtained by integrating equation (5) as follows.

$$(E_s)_{av} = \frac{\int_0^{\pi/2} E_s d\beta}{\pi/2} \quad (6)$$

Figure 10 shows experimental data and calculated values obtained by equations (2)~(6). They agreed very well. Then it is calculated that the erosion rates of mat FRP can be estimated generally.

Figure 9 Evaluation of equation (5) at various volume fractions and α .

Figure 10 Comparison of experimental value with calculated value at various volume fractions and α .

5. Conclusion

The sand erosion behaviors and mechanisms for glass mat FRP were discussed, and following conclusions were obtained.

- (1) The erosion curve of the glass mat composites at any attack angle showed linearity. This behavior was very similar to that of homogeneous materials.
- (2) Glass composites showed brittle behavior in erosion comparing with the resin, and this behavior was emphasized with an increase of glass contents.
- (3) Glass composites showed better resistance than resin at lower attack angle.
- (4) The equation to estimate the erosion rate of mat FRP was proposed.

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